

Exploring Quality Parameters in Lycra-Viscose Core Yarns: A Comparative Analysis of Ring- and Air-Jet Spinning Systems

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Abstract:

The structure and properties of lycra-viscose core-spun yarns manufactured on ring- and air-jet spinning machines have been investigated with respect to ribbon width, filament position, and spinning speed. Under all experimental conditions, the air-jet spun core yarns exhibit lower strength, reduced extensibility, increased hairiness, and inferior abrasion resistance compared to conventional core yarns, however, the positioning of the filament on the roving has a decisive effect on core yarn quality. Core yarns produced with a centered adjustment of the Lycra filament generally demonstrate significantly higher strength and breaking extension, less bulk, reduced hairiness, and inferior abrasion resistance and regularity and more imperfections regardless of the yarn structure. Furthermore, fine air-jet core yarns display a smaller helix diameter, more wrapper fibres, and a higher number of wraps per centimeter. They also possess a larger helix angle than coarse core yarns. An increase in spinning speed results in a higher incidence of wrapper fibres; however, both wraps per centimeter and helix angle initially increase and then decrease with increasing spinning speed.

Keywords: Air-jet spinning, Core-spun yarn, Lycra filament, Ribbon width, Wrapper fibres

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1. Introduction

For numerous years, cotton- wrapped, filament-core spun yarns have been in production [1-5]. However, their widespread utilization is hindered by incomplete core coverage and inadequate strip resistance. To address these limitations [6], introduced various modifications to the conventional core-yarn ring spinning system. Recently, they proposed a novel tandem core-yarn spinning system utilizing air jets and friction drums [7]. Additionally [8], explored the impact of jet spinning parameters on sheath resistance and other related properties of polyester-viscose jet spun yarns [9] delved into the influence of elastane ratio on the mechanical properties of cotton-wrapped elastane-core spun yarns. Textile fabric producers frequently require yarns containing elastomers to produce elastic textile products and accessories. Elastic yarns find applications in diverse market segments such as hosiery, swimwear, sportswear, underwear, and lace, as well as in fashionable clothing. The most common methods of producing elastic yarns include the hollow spindle technique, entangling, twisting, and core spinning on a modified ring frame, as well as rotor, friction, and air-jet spinning. These processes exhibit distinct yarn properties, structures, and yarn count ranges. This study aims to analyze the impact of core positioning, ribbon width, and spinning speed on the structure and properties of lycra-viscose ring- and air-jet spun core yarns.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparations of Yarn Samples

Two sets of elastomeric core yarns, with Tex values of 19.6 and 29.5, were spun using viscose staple fibre with a length of 51 mm and a fineness of 1.66 dtex, in conjunction with Dupont Lycra filament of 63 dtex, on air-jet spinning machine. The specifications of viscose staple and Lycra filament used in the study are given in Table 1. The viscose fibre lap was prepared on Lakshmi Reiter's blow room line and subsequently carded on an MMC carding machine. The conversion to a drawn sliver was executed using Lakshmi Rieters' draw frame DO/2S. Three draw frame passages were given to the carded sliver to produce a finisher sliver of 3 ktex. The drawn silver was then spun into yarns using a Murata air jet spinner 802 MJS. The Lycra filament was positioned on a modified creel and directed to the nip of the front roller with a filament pretension of 45.9 grains. It was

accurately positioned at the center and then at the edge of the drafted ribbon of fibres before being spun into yarns. The process parameters employed to produce these yarns are outlined in Table 2.

Table 1: Specifications of Lycra filament and viscose staple fibre

Fibre/Filament	Length mm	Linear density dtex	Tenacity cN/tex	Breaking elongation %
Viscose	51	1.66	19.42	18.7
Lycra	51	63.18	13.24	716.0

Table 2: Spinning parameters for Lycra viscose MJS core yarns [NP1, 2.5kg/cm²; NP2, 3kg/cm²; Feed ratio, 0.98 and Distance between front nozzle and nip of front roller, 39.5mm

Yarn ref. no.	Yarn tex	Fibre composition (Lycra:Viscose)	Ribbon width mm	Filament position	Spinning speed m/min
S1	19.6	13:87	4	Core	150/170/190
S2	19.6	13:87	4	Side	150/170/190
S3	19.6	13:87	6	Core	150/170/190
S4	19.6	13:87	6	Side	150/170/190
S5	19.6	0:100	0	Nil	150
S6	29.5	9:91	4	Core	150/170/190
S7	29.5	9:91	4	Side	150/170/190
S8	29.5	9:91	6	Core	150/170/190
S9	29.5	9:91	6	Side	150/170/190
S10	29.5	0:100	0	Nil	150

2.2 Test methods

Prior to processing, 0.8% of viscose fibres dyed with red colour were added to the grey fibres during mixing, and the lot was spun into yarns in a normal manner. Subsequently, the yarns were immersed in methyl salicylate with the same refractive index as the fibres, enabling easy observation of the dyed fibres through an image analyzer. Yarn structural parameters, including wrapper fibres, wraps/meter, helix angle, and helix diameter were then measured for sheath fibres using a Leica Q 500 M C image analyzer. For each yarn sample, eighty yarns with both ends shown on the screen were observed. Additionally, the yarns underwent testing for various properties following ASTM standards. These properties included tenacity and breaking extension (Instron), mass irregularity and imperfections (Uster evenness tester), abrasion resistance (Universal wear tester), and hairiness (Zweigles 565 hairiness meter).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Yarn Structural Parameters

3.1.1 Wrapper Fibres

The experimental results for the structural parameters are presented in Table 3. The findings suggest that wrapper fibres are sensitive to the yarn spinning technique, with fewer wrapper fibres observed for core-spun yarns compared to staple spinning. The positioning of the filament at the edge of the fibre ribbon plays a critical role in wrapper fibre formation. The data reveals that placing the filament at the edge of the fibre ribbon leads to a significant reduction in the formation of wrapper fibres. Additionally, the ribbon width is another crucial factor influencing the occurrence of wrapper fibres. As is evident from Table 3, core yarns spun with larger ribbon widths exhibit a higher incidence of wrapper fibres. The increase in wrapper fibres is attributed to the greater number of edge fibres, which later become wrappers after being separated from the main strand due to yarn ballooning action. Among air-jet spun yarns, 19.6 Tex yarns demonstrate a higher incidence of wrapper fibres compared to 29.5 Tex yarns, and this incidence further increases with an increase in spinning speed.

Table 3: Effect of spinning speed, ribbon width and filament position on structural parameters of Lycra-Viscose air-jet spun core yarns [NP1, 2.5kg/cm²; NP2, 3kg/cm²; Feed ratio, 0.98 and Distance between first nozzle and the nip of front roller, 39.5mm]

Yarn Ref. No.	Wrapper fibres/ m			Wraps/cm			Helix diameter, mm			Helix angle, deg		
	150 ^a	170 ⁰	190 ^a	150 ^a	170 ⁰	190 ^a	150 ^a	170 ⁰	190 ^a	150 ^a	170 ⁰	190 ^a
S1	9	10	13	12	14	13	0.138	0.130	0.145	39	43	40
S2	7	9	12	11	13	12	0.148	0.144	0.144	38	39	41
S3	11	14	16	14	16	15	0.123	0.121	0.141	42	44	41
S4	9	12	14	12	14	13	0.131	0.124	0.125	41	43	41
S5	11	11	11	13	13	13	0.138	0.138	0.138	44	44	44
S6	5	6	10	8	11	9	0.208	0.198	0.217	38	39	39
S7	4	5	8	7	10	8	0.212	0.203	0.209	38	39	38
S8	8	11	13	10	13	11	0.180	0.173	0.184	40	45	42
S9	6	10	12	9	11	10	0.184	0.183	0.185	40	42	40
S10	7	7	7	9	9	9	0.204	0.204	0.204	41	41	41

^a Spinning speed, m/min

3.1.2 Wraps/m

Table 3 displays the wraps/m concerning different spinning parameters. It is observed that as the yarn linear density decreases from 29.5 to 19.6 Tex, there is a noticeable increase in wraps/m, as expected. In comparison with 100% viscose yarn, core yarns exhibit fewer wrapper fibres, possibly due to increased balloon tension resulting from the higher retraction power of the elastomeric component. This, in turn, disturbs the ballooning action and leads to the generation of wild fibres. While the positioning of the Lycra filament at the edge of the ribbon produces a yarn with fewer wraps/m, the use of a larger ribbon width can enhance wraps/m. On increasing the spinning speed, the wraps/m initially increases but reduces thereafter as the spinning speed is raised to 190m/min. The air flow at the nip of the front roller at higher speed causes the fibres to move away from the fibre bundle, resulting in longer and even wrappings. However, a further increase in spinning speed causes the filament to bounce back to the original position, which, in turn, results in uneven wrapping and consequently decreased wraps/m.

3.1.3 Helix Diameter and Helix Angle

Changes in both yarn linear density and filament position can affect helix diameter and helix angle, although 100% viscose staple yarn is generally bulkier than air-jet spun core yarns (Table 3). When the spinning speed is increased from 150 m/min to 170 m/min, the helix diameter of air-jet core yarns reduces considerably but starts to increase at 190 m/min spinning speed. The initial reduction in helix diameter arises due to more uniform, even, and tight wrappings of wrapper fibres, which later become more irregular at high spinning speeds. The helix diameter of all the yarns produced with a 6 mm ribbon width, however, is much larger than the yarns produced with a 4 mm ribbon width. For all experimental combinations, the helix angle maintains a relationship that coincides with wraps/m.

3.2 Tensile Properties

Table 4 illustrates that the air-jet spun core yarns, whether produced with Lycra filament positioned at the edge or at the center of the ribbon, are weaker than the conventional core yarn. However, the contribution of the wrap material to the overall yarn tenacity is minimal in both methods. The lower tenacity of air-jet core yarn can be attributed to its unique structure. For both types of yarn structures, the core-spun yarn with the Lycra filament core exhibits significantly lower tenacity than that of the 100% viscose staple yarn. This may be explained by assuming that core spinning lacks good fibre control compared to staple spinning. When comparing the two core-spun yarns, the one spun with centered adjustment on the roving shows markedly higher tenacity than that of the core yarn produced with core at the edge of the roving. Surprisingly, however, the tenacity of air-jet spun core yarns first increases significantly and then drops with increasing spinning speed. This is due to the increase in the incidence of wrapper fibres with increasing spinning speed from 150 m/min to 170 m/min, which produces a compact structural matrix due to increased radial pressure on core fibres. However, at 190 m/min spinning speed, the fibres are less compact due to increased yarn unevenness. Consequently, there is less radial pressure on core fibres, affecting the average value of packing density and yarn tenacity. On the other hand, a consistent decrease in core yarn tenacity with an increase in ribbon width could be related to the large reduction in load bearing core fibres [10]. Regarding yarn linear density, yarn tenacity shows opposite trends for ring- and air-jet spun core

yarns. In the case of ring-spun yarns, the tenacity is lower, as usual, for finer yarns. However, for air-jet spun yarns, the tenacity is higher for 19.5 Tex yarns, and it decreases as the yarn linear density increases to 29.5 tex.

Table 4: Effect of spinning speed, ribbon width and filament position on tenacity, breaking extension, diameter and abrasion resistance of Lycra-Viscose ring- and air-jet spun core Yarns [NP1, 2.5kg/cm²; NP2, 3kg/cm²; Feed ratio,0.98 and Distance between first nozzle and the nip of front roller,39.5mm

Yarn Ref. No.	Tenacity, g/tex				Breaking extension, %				Diameter, mm				Abrasion resistance, cycles			
	Ring yarn	Air- jet yarn			Ring yarn	Air- jet yarn			Ring yarn	Air-jet yarn			Ring yarn	Air-jet yarn		
		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a
S1	11.5	10.2	10.4	10.2	11.2	9.3	9.5	9.9	0.168	0.158	0.150	0.162	305	223	258	234
S2	11.2	9.5	9.8	9.2	11.0	9.1	9.2	9.6	0.170	0.167	0.163	0.169	340	236	269	253
S3	11.5	8.8	9.4	8.9	11.2	8.8	9.4	9.5	0.168	0.145	0.139	0.158	305	256	287	266
S4	11.2	8.6	9.3	7.9	11.0	8.2	9.1	9.3	0.170	0.147	0.146	0.150	340	290	293	276
S5	14.2	10.9	10.9	10.9	12.2	7.9	7.9	7.9	0.164	0.157	0.157	0.157	78	53	53	53
S6	12.9	9.8	10.1	9.7	12.9	8.4	8.9	9.0	0.228	0.226	0.217	0.218	376	241	301	278
S7	12.7	8.9	9.2	9.0	12.7	8.2	8.7	8.8	0.235	0.230	0.222	0.226	419	320	339	300
S8	12.9	9.1	9.3	8.8	12.9	8.0	8.5	8.8	0.228	0.203	0.189	0.202	376	295	363	350
S9	12.7	8.6	9.1	8.0	12.7	6.8	7.3	7.6	0.235	0.205	0.202	0.200	419	359	390	371
S10	15.0	10.1	10.1	10.1	12.8	6.8	6.8	6.8	0.226	0.219	0.219	0.219	88	67	67	67

^a Spinning speed, m/min.

Invariably, ring- and air-jet spun core yarns exhibit higher breaking extension than that of 100% viscose staple yarn. However, air-jet spun core yarns are less extensible than their ring-spun counterparts. On the other hand, the breaking extension of air-jet core yarn spun with a centered filament position is much higher compared to the core yarn spun with the filament positioned at the edge of the roving. Both yarn linear density and ribbon width play a significant role in influencing breaking extension. As can be seen from Table 4, the breaking extension is appreciably low in coarse core yarns, and it decreases further with an increase in ribbon width. This may probably arise from a high wrapper -to- core fibre ratio that makes the yarn insufficient to sustain tensile loading, leading to a decrease in breaking extension. Changes in spinning speed also has a marked impact on yarn breaking extension, and the core yarns spun with a higher spinning speed have much higher breaking extension.

3.3 Bulk

Table 4 compares the diameters of lycra-viscose ring- and air-jet spun core yarns. Generally, air-jet spun core yarns possess less bulk than their ring-spun counterparts, and its variance depends on the experimental conditions used. The lesser bulk of air-jet spun core yarns results from a higher incidence of wrapper fibres and wraps/m, causing the structural matrix to become more compact. On the other hand, lycra-viscose core yarns, whether produced on ring- or air jet spinner, are bulkier than 100% viscose staple yarn owing to poor fibre control exercised during core yarn spinning. Among the air-jet spun core yarns, the yarn spun with the centrally positioned filament has less bulk than that of the core yarn produced with the filament at the edge of the ribbon. The impact of yarn linear density is along the expected lines, a higher linear density results in higher bulk. As the spinning speed increases, the bulk of air-jet spun core yarns first reduces significantly and then increases. This is because of higher fibre cohesion attained at higher spinning speeds due to the presence of more wrapper fibres and hence compact yarn. However, at a spinning speed of 190 m/min, uneven and irregular wrappings are formed, which, in turn, exerts less radial pressure on the core fibres, resulting in a larger yarn diameter. Furthermore, the average yarn bulk reduces significantly with an increase in ribbon width.

3.4 Abrasion Resistance

Table 4 depicts the number of rubs required to rupture lycra-viscose ring- and air-jet spun core yarns. Invariably, core-spun yarns exhibit higher abrasion resistance than 100% viscose staple yarn, regardless of the spinning system used. This is quite understandable and is the result of high abrasion resistance of the Lycra filament present in the core yarn. Amongst air-jet spun core yarns, the one spun with the filament positioned at the edge of the ribbon displays much higher abrasion resistance than that spun with filament positioned at the center, the presence of a high abrasion- resistant filament at the surface reduces the intensity of abrading action. Increasing spinning speed from 150 m/min to 170 m/min enhances the abrasion resistance of air-jet spun core yarns due to an increased incidence of wrapper fibres. However, a further increase in spinning speed no longer favors an increase in abrasion resistance on account of decreased packing density. Moreover, abrasion resistance increases with an increase in both yarn linear density and ribbon width.

3.5 Hairiness

Table 5 shows the hairiness of different yarns. Under all experimental conditions, the hairiness of core-spun yarns is generally higher than that of 100% viscose staple yarn. This is an expected consequence of poor fibre control exercised in core spinning compared to staple spinning control. However, the core-spun yarn with the centered adjustment of the filament core has much less hairiness than that of the core-spun yarn produced with the core at the edge of the ribbon. On the other hand, the hairiness of air-jet spun core yarns tends to increase with an increase in spinning speed and ribbon width, owing to an increase in number of floating fibres [11]. When comparing ring- and air-jet spun core yarns, the hairiness of the former is lower. However, the variation in hairiness is greater for the air-jet spun yarns than for the ring-spun yarns. Hairiness increases with increasing yarn linear density for both ring- and air-jet spun yarns.

Table 5: Effect of spinning speed, ribbon width and filament position on hairiness, unevenness and imperfections of lycra-viscose ring- and air-jet spun core yarns [NP1, 2.5kg/cm²; NP2,3kg/cm²; Feed ratio 0.98 and Distance between first nozzle and the nip of front roller,39.5mm]

Yarn ref. no	Hairs/10m				Unevenness, U%				Imperfections/100m			
	Ring yarn	Air-jet yarn			Ring yarn	Air-jet yarn			Ring yarn	Air-jet yarn		
		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a		150 ^a	170 ^a	190 ^a
S1	62	51	82	94	10.7	13.1	12.4	11.6	4	22	12	13
S2	65	70	90	108	11.1	12.5	12.3	11.1	8	19	24	30
S3	62	104	156	200	10.7	12.8	12.4	12.0	5	14	20	15
S4	65	108	180	202	11.1	12.7	12.6	12.3	8	17	12	15
S5	47	59	59	59	11.7	13.1	13.1	13.1	9	20	20	20
S6	64	83	104	116	9.5	12.8	12.3	11.6	3	5	33	8
S7	68	126	132	176	10.1	12.3	10.8	10.6	8	4	7	22
S8	64	210	232	242	9.5	12.6	12.2	12.1	3	6	12	12
S9	68	282	313	234	10.1	11.4	11.0	11.0	8	5	6	5
S10	50	53	53	53	11.5	13.0	13.0	13.0	9	14	14	14

^a Speed, m/min

3.6 Unevenness and Imperfections

Table 5 shows that Uster values (U %) and imperfection figures for core-spun yarns are generally much less than those for 100% viscose staple yarn. Although thin places (-50%) per 1000- meter length of the 100% viscose staple yarn are considerably higher than that of the core-spun yarns, the other IPI values (imperfections per 1000 meter) are very close to those for the three types of yarns produces on the air-jet spinner. This suggests that core-spun yarn spinning process does not adversely affect yarn evenness and imperfections.

4. Conclusions

Yarn characteristics in air-jet spun core yarns are influenced by factors like linear density, ribbon width, spinning speed, and filament position. Fine air-jet spun core yarns have smaller helix diameter, more wrapper fibres, and wraps/cm, along with a larger helix angle compared to coarse core yarns. Increasing spinning speed generally leads to more wrapper fibres, but wraps/cm and helix angle initially increase and then decrease. Placing the filament at the center increases wrapper fibres and wraps/cm but reduces helix diameter. Larger ribbon width in core yarns results in a larger helix diameter, smaller helix angle and more wrapper fibres and wraps/cm.

Air-jet spun core yarns, overall, are weaker, less extensible, hairier, and have poor abrasion resistance compared to conventional core yarns. However, filament positioning on the roving significantly affects core yarn quality. Core yarns with a centered lycra filament display higher strength and breaking extension, less bulk, less hairiness, poorer abrasion resistance, regularity, and more imperfections, irrespective of yarn structure.

High spinning speed is crucial for air-jet spinning to generate ample wrapper fibres. The optimal speed around 170 m/min, depends on factors like filament position, ribbon width, and yarn linear density. Inadequate wrapper fibres result from a too-small ribbon width, leading to a weak yarn. Conversely, an overly large ribbon increases wrapper fibres, negatively impacting yarn regularity and hairiness. While thin places in 100% viscose staple yarn exceed core-spun yarns, other imperfections per 1000-meter values are similar. This suggests that core-spun yarn spinning process does not detrimentally affect yarn evenness and imperfections.

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